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COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF MARKET SAMPLE OF PHALATRIKADI KWATH WITH IT'S REFERANCE STANDARD

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Abstract

Background: In Ayurvedic Classics, a number of single drugs and formulations have been mentioned. *Phalatrikadi Kwath* is one of the significant and known formulations that is successfully used from the ancient period. Standardization of formulation is essential for promoting safe, effective, and reliable herbal products in the market.

Material & Method:

Powder microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India was carried out. Slides of *Phalatrikadi Kwath* were prepared using the required reagent and observed under the microscope.

Observation & Result:

Powder microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath* shows the presence of Epicarp, Parenchyma from the mesocarp, Prismatic crystal, stone cells fibers, stomata, parenchymatous cells with starch grains and oil globules and trichome etc.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The microscopic features which were observed in the *Phalatrikadi Kwath* procured from the market revealed that it contains, *Kalmegha* (*Andrographis paniculata* Nees), *Vasa* (*Adhathoda vasica* Nees), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb)Miers), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss), *Haritaki*(*Terminalia chebula* Retz.), *Bibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb), *Amalaki* (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn), *Katuki* (*Picrorhiza kurroa* Royle Ex Benth).

Key Words:

Phalatrikadi Kwath, Powder microscopy, Standardization of Herbal Formulations

INTRODUCTION:

One of the special contributions of our old Ayurvedic seers is *Phalatrikadi Kwath*. It is a great combo of eight medications with a variety of effects. In the context of *Pandu* and *Kamala*, *Phalatrikadi Kwath* formulation was described in Chakradatta (8/8), Sharangdhar Samhita (2/75), Yoga Ratnakar (5th sloka), and Bhaisajya Ratnavali (12/22).ⁱ

Eight medications found in *Phalatrikadi Kwath* are mostly effective in treating cirrhosis, alcoholic hepatitis, fatty liver, *Koshthashrit Kamala*, or hepatocellular jaundice, and other liver conditions. Due to the properties like-*Pitta-Kaphashamaka*, *Yakriduttejaka*, *Shothahara*, *Pandurogahara*, *Rechan*, *Deepan* etc. *Phalatrikadi Kwath* taken with honey pacify the *Koshthashrit kamala* and *Pandu*.ⁱⁱ

First described in Chakradatta written by Chakrapanidutta in 11th century and later on many texts, is the most popular and effective preparation contains the eight herbs namely. *Kalmegha* (*Andrographis paniculata* Nees), *Vasa* (*Adhathoda vasica* A.Juss), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb)Miers), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A Juss), *Haritaki*(*Terminalia chebula* Retz), *Bibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb), *Amalaki* (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn), *Katuki* (*Picrorhiza kurroa* Royle Ex Benth).ⁱⁱⁱ

AIM:

To study the powder microscopic features of *Phalatrikadi kwath* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

OBJECTIVE:

To study the powder microscopic features of *Phalatrikadi kwath* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India

To compare the microscopic features of the *Phalatrikadi kwath* formulation with their standards of each of the individual ingredient mentioned in Reference standard.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sample of *Phalatrikadi kwath* was procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India in the month of October 2024. The study was performed at Pharmacognosy Laboratory of Upgraded Department of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*, Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara, Gujarat.

Slide preparation:

Slide of *Phalatrikadi kwath* procured from the market was prepared using required reagent and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in Reference standard.

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder Microscopic features of found in *Phalatrikadi kwath* Market Sample.

Sr.no	Microscopic features	<i>Kalmegha</i> (<i>Andrographis</i>)	<i>Vasa</i> (<i>Adhatoda</i> Ness)	<i>Guduchi</i> (<i>Tinospora</i> Miers)	<i>Nimba</i> (<i>Azadirachta</i> A.Juss.)	<i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia</i> Linn.)	<i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia</i> Linn.)	<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Emmilia</i> Gaertn.)	<i>Katuki</i> (<i>Picrorhiza</i> Royl.)
1.	Glandular trichomes	+							
2.	Fragment of simple trichome from the anther	+							
3.	Stomata	+							
4.	Upper epidermis in surface view	+							
5.	Simple trichome		+						
6.	Sessile glandular trichome		+						
7.	Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate		+						
8.	Tracheids			+					
9.	Fibers			+	+				
10.	Stone Cells				+				
11.	Sclereids				+				
12.	Epidermis					+			
13.	Epidermal hairs						+		
14.	Parenchymatous cells with starch grains and oil globules						+		

15.	Trichome							+		
16.	Epicarp								+	
17.	Prismatic crystal of silica								+	
18.	Starch grain				+				+	+
19.	Fiber								+	
20.	Cork in surface view									+
21.	Cells with orange colored content									+

Table No. 2: Microscopic features in reference standard^{iv} compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Kalmegha (Andrographis paniculata* Nees) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Kalmegha (Andrographis paniculata)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Glandular trichomes	+	[Fig. 1.a]
2.	Fragment of simple trichome from the anther	+	[Fig. 1.b]
3.	Stomata	+	[Fig. 1.c]
4.	Upper epidermis in surface view	+	[Fig. 1.d]

Table No. 3: Microscopic features in reference standard^v compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Vasa (Adhathoda vasica* Nees) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Vasa (Adhathoda vasica)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Simple trichome	+	[Fig. 2.a]
2.	Sessile glandular trichome	+	[Fig. 2.b]
3.	Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate	+	[Fig. 2.c]

Table No. 4: Microscopic features in reference standard^{vi} compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb)Miers) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Guduchi</i> (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>) in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Tracheids	+	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Fiber	+	[Fig. 3.b]

Table No. 5: Microscopic features in reference standard ^{vii} compared with Powder microscopic feature of found in sample *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Nimba</i> (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>) in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Fibers	+	[Fig.4.a]
2.	Stone Cells	+	[Fig. 4.b]
3.	Sclereids	+	[Fig. 4.c]
4.	Starch Grain	+	[Fig. 4.d]

Table No.6: Microscopic features in reference standard ^{viii} compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>) in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Epidermis	+	[Fig. 5.a]

Table No.7: Microscopic features in reference standard ^{ix} compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Bibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>) in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Epidermal hairs	+	[Fig. 6.a]
2.	Parenchymatous cells with starch grains and oil globules	+	[Fig. 6.b]

3.	Trichome	+	[Fig. 6.c]
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Table No.8: Microscopic features in reference standard^x compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Amalaki (Emblca officinalis Gaertn)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Amalaki (Emblca officinalis)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Epicarp	+	[Fig. 7.a]
2.	Prismatic crystal of silica	+	[Fig. 7.b]
3.	Starch grain	+	[Fig. 7.c]
4.	Fiber	+	[Fig. 7.d]

Table No.9: Microscopic features in reference standard^{xi} compared with Powder microscopic feature of found in *Katuki (Picrorhiza kurroa Royle Ex Benth)* sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Katuki (Picrorhiza kurroa)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Cork in surface view	+	[Fig. 8.a]
2.	Cells with orange colored content	+	[Fig. 8.b]
3.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 8.c]

- Absent, + Present

This study provides information about the microscopic characteristics of the herbal formulation *Phalatrikadi Kwath* that was purchased from the local market. Which contains *Kalmegha (Andrographis paniculata Nees)*, *Vasa (Adhathoda vasica Nees)*, *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (Thunb) Miers)*, *Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss)*, *Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz)*, *Bibhitaki (Terminalia bellirica Roxb)*, *Amalaki (Emblca officinalis Gaertn)*, *Katuki (Picrorhiza kurroa Royle Ex Benth)*. The powder of *Phalatrikadi Kwath* was chosen for this microscopic study. *Phalatrikadi Kwath's* powder-microscopic features have been observed and will be explained in more detail.

Phalatrikadi Kwath powder microscopy indicates the following: presence of Glandular trichomes, Fragment of simple trichome from the anther, Stomata, Upper epidermis in surface view suggests that it contains *Kalmegha (Andrographis paniculata Nees)*; presence of Simple trichome, Sessile glandular trichome, Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate suggests that it contains *Vasa (Adhathoda vasica Nees)*; presence of Tracheids, fiber suggests it contains *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (Thunb) Miers)*; presence of Fibers, Stone Cells, Sclereids, Starch Grain suggests it contains *Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss)*; presence of Epidermis, suggests it contains *Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz)*; presence of Epidermal hairs, Parenchymatous cells with starch grains and oil globules, Trichome suggests it contains *Bibhitaki (Terminalia bellirica Roxb)*; presence of Epicarp, Prismatic crystal of silica, Starch grain, Fiber suggests it contains *Amalaki (Emblca officinalis Gaertn)*; and presence of Cork in surface view, Cells with orange colored content, Starch grains suggests it contains *Katuki (Picrorhiza kurroa Royle Ex Benth)*.

CONCLUSION:

Kalmegha (*Andrographis paniculata* Nees), *Vasa* (*Adhathoda vasica* Nees), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb)Miers), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz), *Bibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb), *Amalaki* (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn), *Katuki* (*Picrorhiza kurroa* Royle Ex Benth) are key ingredients of *Phalatrikadi Kwath*.

Microscopic key identifications of features of *Kalmegha* (*Andrographis paniculata* Nees), *Vasa* (*Adhathoda vasica* Nees), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb)Miers), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz), *Bibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb), *Amalaki* (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn), *Katuki* (*Picrorhiza kurroa* Royle Ex Benth) are as follows:

Sr. no.	Plant	Key identification features
1.	<i>Kalmegha</i> (<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees)	Glandular trichomes, Fragment of simple trichome from the anther, Stomata, Upper epidermis in surface view
2.	<i>Vasa</i> (<i>Adhathoda vasica</i> Nees)	Simple trichome, Sessile glandular trichome, Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate
3.	<i>Guduchi</i> (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Thunb)Miers)	Tracheids, Fiber
4.	<i>Nimba</i> (<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss)	Fibers, Stone Cells, Sclereids, Starch grains
5.	<i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz)	Epidermis
6.	<i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> Roxb)	Epidermal hairs, Parenchymatous cells with starch grains and oil globules, Trichome
7.	<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Emblica officinalis</i> Gaertn)	Epicarp, Prismatic crystal of silica, Starch grain, Fiber
8.	<i>Katuki</i> (<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i> Royle Ex Benth)	Cork in surface view, Cells with orange colored content, Starch grains

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Plate No. 1: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath– Kalmegha (Andrographis paniculata* Nees)

Fig. 1(a). Glandular trichomes

Fig. 1(b). Fragment of simple trichome from

Fig. 1(c). Stomata

Fig. 1(d). Upper epidermis in surface view

Plate No. 2: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath – Vasa (Adhathoda vasica* Nees)

Fig. 2(a). Simple trichome

Fig. 2(b). Sessile glandular trichome

Fig. 2(c). Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate

Plate No. 3: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath – Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb)Miers)

Fig. 3(a). Tracheids

Fig. 3(b). Fiber

Plate No. 4: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath – Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss)

Fig. 4(a). Fiber

Fig. 4(b). Stone cells

Fig. 4(c). Sclereids

Fig. 4(d). Starch grains

**Plate No. 5: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath – Haritaki*
(*Terminalia chebula* Retz.)**

Fig. 5(a). Epidermis

**Plate No. 6: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath – Bibhitaki*
(*Terminalia bellirica* Roxb)**

Fig. 6(a). Epidermal cells

Fig. 6(b). Parenchymatous cells with starch grains and oil globules

Fig. 6(c). Trichome

Plate No. 7: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Phalatrikadi Kwath-Amalaki (Emblca officinalis Gaertn)*

Fig. 7(a). Epicarp

Fig. 7(b). Prismatic crystal

Fig. 7(c). Starch grains

Fig. 7(d). Fiber

Plate No. 8: Photos of Powder Microscopy of Phalatrikadi Kwath – Katuki (*Picrorhiza kurroa* Royle Ex Benth)

Fig. 8(a). Cork in surface view

Fig. 8(b). Cells with orange colored content

Fig. 8(c). Starch grains

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